

ENTERING THROUGH THEIR DOOR— BUT NOT GETTING STUCK THERE Theological and Missional Engagement in Acts 17:16-34

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Abstract: The prophetic nature of the life-mission of a disciple of Jesus resides precisely in living the daily tension of being deeply rooted *in* the world, but not being *of* the world. The difficulty experienced in walking the tightrope in such a situation, indeed is the guarantee of one's faithfulness to the Lord. Such difficulties should never be resolved by means of compromise. We see such a tension in Acts 17:16-34.

Keywords: Prophetic Mission, Fidelity, Unknown God, Idolatry, Discipleship.

INTRODUCTION

To be relevant and effective, it is important to 'move with the times' in our life-mission. However, when the 'moving with the times' takes the form of 'playing to the gallery,' 'scoring brownie points,' and finally leading to 'being carried along the stream like a dry twig,' or even 'floating along the currents' like a dead fish, one needs to seriously introspect. The prophetic nature of the life-mission of a disciple of Jesus resides precisely in living the daily tension of being

deeply rooted *in* the world, but not being *of* the world. The difficulty experienced in walking the tightrope in such a situation, indeed is the guarantee of one's faithfulness to the Lord. Such difficulties should never be resolved by means of compromise. We see such a tension in Acts 17:16-34. Paul's encounter with some Athenian citizens at the Areopagus encourages us to enter through 'their door' but cautions us against settling down there. The development and the ending of this text offers some valuable insights for a meaningful engagement with the worldviews, cultures, ideologies, political-economic systems and individuals whom a disciple of Jesus can't fully agree with.

1. THE LUCAN CONTEXTUAL SETTING AND THE DYNAMICS OF THE TEXT (ACTS 17:16-34)

Although Luke's explicit addressee in both of his books (the Gospel and the Acts) is Theophilus (Lk 1:3; Acts 1:1), his implied reader is a predominantly Gentile Christian, Greek-speaking, urban community, facing social marginalization. However, in his community the existence of at least a minority of Christians of Jewish background cannot be ruled out. In addition, the Lucan community faces a faith crisis regarding the faithfulness of God in Jesus Christ, since God's faithfulness to Jewish people itself is doubted in the context of the destruction of the Jerusalem temple in 70 AD. That makes Luke's *Sitz-im-Leben*. Hence, his task would be to show God's inclusive faithfulness to all those who repent—Jews and gentiles. Within this broad framework, the narrative of Acts 17:16-34 is Luke's construction of Paul's encounter with Athenian philosophers. Paul's stay in Athens is mentioned in 1 Thess 3:1. The aim of Luke's construction of 'Paul at Athens' is to instruct his audience "about the great opportunity and the immense stumbling block of any mission to the Hellenistic intelligentsia (Acts 16-21)."¹

¹ R. J. Dillon, "Acts of the Apostles," in *The New Jerome Biblical Commentary*, ed. Raymond E. Brown, Joseph A. Fitzmyer, and Roland E. Murphy (London:

In his construction Luke shows adequate knowledge of Paul's original *Sitz-im-Leben* and his theology, which in turn are interpreted through the lens of Luke's own redactional concerns.² This leads us to witness the unfolding of a two-tier 'drama': (a) the constructed story-line of Paul at Athens and (b) the deep story of Luke's address to his community. The common factor in both of them is summarized in the title of this article: it is *entering through their door... but not getting stuck there*.

This leads us to affirm a triple contextuality of the Lucan text: (a) it refers to Paul's mission at Athens and contains some details of that context, possibly drawn from the available Pauline sources. (b) Luke has his own historical context while creating this literary construct called *Paul at Athens*.³ Besides a few decades of temporal distance from Paul's audience, Luke's own audience has different socio-cultural settings. (c) Luke's literary context in Acts 17 forms the third layer of the context. By considering the text within the framework of all these layers, I intend to draw inspiration for our own 'real world' issues that are mentioned in the introduction.

In Luke's *Sitz-im-Leben* the proclamation of Christ was two-pronged: promotion of monotheism and a Hellenistic-Jewish presentation of the Christian faith.⁴ The Lucan

Prince Hall, 1990), 754.

² Dibelius, however opines: "the theology of the Areopagus speech is absolutely foreign to Paul's own theology, ... it is, in fact, foreign to the entire New Testament." M. Dibelius, "Paul on the Areopagus," in *Studies in the Acts of the Apostles*, ed. Heinrich Greeven (New York: Charles Scribner's Sons; London: SCM Press, 1956), 71, cited in Joseph A. Fitzmyer, *The Acts of the Apostles (The Anchor Bible 31; New York: Doubleday, 1998)*, 602. A few others too have similar opinions. Notwithstanding such critique, one cannot miss some traces of Pauline theology as well as the OT phraseology in the Lucan text.

³ Various scholars referred to in commentaries such as *New Jerome Biblical Commentary*, *The New Interpreter's Bible: A Commentary in Twelve Volumes*, *Anchor Bible*, and *Sacra Pagina* agree that it is hard to consider that Paul actually had such an encounter at Athens in all the details that Luke provides.

⁴ L. Legrand, "The Areopagus Speech," in *La notion biblique de Dieu*, ed. J. Coppens (Leuven, 1976), 342-345, cited in Dillon, "Acts of the Apostles," 755.

Paul's attempt to integrate the Greek 'unitary cosmos' with the Jewish 'bipartite world'⁵ in the statement "world and everything" (Acts 17:24) perhaps reflects Luke's own contextual concerns more than that of Paul in Athens.

In Acts 3:17 and 13:27, the 'times of ignorance' is attributed to the Jews who did not accept Jesus, but in Acts 17:30 it is used to indicate the state of the Gentiles regarding their ideas about the divine. The merciful God of Luke's conception, however, does not hold it against either of them. It is in tandem with Paul's own depiction of the forbearance or righteousness of God in Rom 3:25. Here, Luke is faithful to the Pauline thought. God's universal mercy calls for 'universal repentance' (Acts 17:30). There is no partiality here. Such an appeal resonates well with Lk 24:47. While proclaiming such mercy, Lucan Paul does not refrain from asserting that merely 'natural revelation' is not sufficient for salvation. It needs to be corrected and supplemented by what is revealed in Jesus Christ.⁶

The underlying statement at Acts 17:16-17 is that neither scholarly learning in Athens nor the presence of the Jewish synagogue has been effective in getting rid of the idol worship there.⁷ Luke strategically focuses Paul's speech on the 'altar dedicated to an unknown god,' by editing the actual references to the altars to unknown gods (plural) in the Greek world.⁸ However, the Lucan construct of Paul's

⁵ Dillon, "Acts of the Apostles," 755.

⁶ L. T. Johnson, "The Acts of the Apostles," in *Sacra Pagina*, vol. 5, ed. Daniel J. Harrington (Collegeville, MN: Liturgical Press, 1992), 317.

⁷ R. W. Wall, "The Acts of the Apostles," in *The New Interpreter's Bible: A Commentary in Twelve Volumes*, vol. 10, ed. Leander E. Keck et al. (Nashville: Abingdon Press, 2002), 243.

⁸ An altar at Athens with the inscription "an unknown god" (*Agnosto Theo*) is not discovered to date. Ancient Greek authors speak of Athenian *bomoi theon onomazomenon agnoston* (altars of gods called unknown) (Pausanias, *Descr. Graec.* 1.1.4; cf. 5.14.8; Philostratus, *Vita Apollonii* 6.3.5 [agnoston daimonon bomoi]; Diogenes Laertius, *Vitae* I.110). Such altars were apparently set up under the direction of Epimenides of Crete (see Diogenes Laertius, *Epimenides* I.10.110 [*Athenaiōn bomoi anonymoi*, "altars of Athenians with no name on

preaching against idols is not foreign to Paul's own thinking. In fact, to the Thessalonians he wrote: "You turned to God from idols, to serve a living and true God" (1 Thess 1:9).

2. THE LUCAN DEPICTION OF THE GREEK WORLD OF PAUL'S ENCOUNTER

In our text, the Stoic and the Epicurean philosophers are the primary interlocutors of Paul (Acts 17:18). The Stoics were known for their piety in terms of their trust in the divine immanence and providence. These attitudes took the form of a true religious spirit in the thinking of Marcus Aurelius and Epictetus.⁹ However, the Epicureans, generally speaking admired only their founder, while being 'impious' in all other things.¹⁰ Acts 17:26 depicts God's intentional creation and especially that of human beings. Thereby it negates the Epicurean idea of a 'chance event' in the emerging of the world. God's providence indeed brings about and sustains the world.¹¹

The Stoic and Epicurean philosophers treat Paul with respect and show eagerness to listen to him (Acts 17:19) despite calling him a 'babbling' (*spermologos*, v. 18) – literally, a bird that picks seeds at one place and drops them at another – a metaphor for a gossip or a peddler of old ideas.¹² Such a branding stands in contrast to what Athenian philosophers were usually interested in: new ideas.

them"])). Indeed St. Jerome, referring to this part of the text of Acts commented: "The altar's inscription was not, as Paul stated, 'To the unknown god,' but 'To the gods of Asia, Europe, and Africa, unknown and foreign gods'" (*Comm. in Titum* 1.12; PL 26.607), cited in Fitzmyer, *The Acts of the Apostles*, 607; also see Diogenes Laertius, *Lives of Eminent Philosophers* 1:110; Philostratus, *Life of Apollonius of Tyana* 6:3, cited in Johnson, "The Acts of the Apostles," 315.

⁹ Cf. Marcus Aurelius, *Meditations* 1:17; 2:3; 2:11–12; 4:23; 5:7–8, and Epictetus, *Discourses* 1.16.15–21; 3.5.8–11; 3.22.2–8; 4.1.89, cited in Johnson, "The Acts of the Apostles," 313.

¹⁰ Plutarch, *Reply to Colotes* 17 [Moralia 1117 B–C], cited in Johnson, "The Acts of the Apostles," 313.

¹¹ Fitzmyer, *The Acts of the Apostles*, 605.

¹² Philostratus, *Life of Apollonius of Tyana* 5:20; Philo, *Embassy to Gaius* 203, cited in Johnson, "The Acts of the Apostles," 313.

However, their disdain gradually gives rise to curiosity at Acts 17:21, where the philosophers show interest in hearing something ‘new’ from Paul. To be sure, the philosophers that Paul encountered were not idolaters. The Epicureans did not believe in any deity; and the Stoics believed in a deity in whom “we live, move, and have our being” (Acts 17:28).¹³ Idolatry belonged predominantly to the folk religion.

R. Garland reports of the three conditions that were necessary for ushering in a new religion in Athens: (a) the usher should represent the ‘new’ deity or religion; (b) he must establish the new deity’s interest to dwell in Athens, and (c) such a dwelling should benefit the Athenians.¹⁴ Paul fulfils the first condition in Acts 17:23. However, the ‘new deity’ of Paul’s proclamation does not need any specific residence or a fresh insertion into the Greek pantheon. The ‘new deity’ not only transcends all spaces but also does not need any Greek type of worship (Acts 17:24-29).¹⁵ In fact, the deity of Paul’s proclamation judges and saves all those who repent through the resurrection of Jesus (Acts 17:30-31)—a benefit according to the third condition, is ironically not being grasped by Paul’s hearers.

3. THE PERSONALITY OF THE LUCAN PAUL

Paul is cast as Socrates for trying to bring in ‘foreign deities’ into Athens (Acts 17:18). The latter was charged with a similar accusation: “He believes not in the gods the city believes in, but in other strange deities (*hetera daimonia kaina*).”¹⁶ The Athenians took Paul’s word “resurrection” (feminine noun *anastasis*) for a female deity, a consort of god Jesus. Hence the plural, “foreign deities,” refers to “Jesus and Anastasis.”¹⁷ Paul’s ‘debate’ (*dialogomai*) in Acts

¹³ Wall, “The Acts of the Apostles,” 244.

¹⁴ R. Garland, *Introducing New Gods: The Politics of Athenian Religion* (London: Duckworth, 1992), 18-19. Referred to in Wall, “The Acts of the Apostles,” 245.

¹⁵ Wall, “The Acts of the Apostles,” 245.

¹⁶ Plato, *Apology* 11§248, cited in Fitzmyer, *The Acts of the Apostles*, 605. Plato, *Apol.* 24b; *Xenophon, Memorabilia* 1.1.1. Cited in Dillon, “Acts of the Apostles,” 754.

¹⁷ Rudolf Bultmann, *Theology of the New Testament* (trans. Kendrick Grobel;

17:2 resembles the philosophizing style of Socrates.¹⁸ The expression, “He argued... also in the marketplace every day with those who happened to be there” (Acts 17:17) further casts him as Socrates, who in turn was known for awakening in the people a new awareness by means of his questions.¹⁹

Luke’s strategy of presenting Paul as a type of Socrates is seen by some as aimed at depicting him as the “model for philosophical integrity” in his response to his accusers, as Socrates was.²⁰ Paul, on his part would respond to those who suspected him by presenting Jesus as the judge.²¹ In addition, we note that Areopagus was considered as one of those authoritative spaces like other councils mentioned in the Acts in the context of having public debates and giving verdicts. Hence, in the Lucan depiction, taking Paul to Areopagus (Acts 17:19) could indicate a test to authenticate his intellectual standing in his ‘strange teaching.’²² Lucan Paul, in effect, resembles a “Jewish [Christian] preacher addressing a pagan audience about the true God.”²³

With this background, we shall now trace the Lucan Paul’s strategy of entering through ‘their door.’

4. PAUL’S ENTRY THROUGH THEIR DOOR

Luke shows a remarkable skill in constructing a Paul who begins where his audience are. In fact, it is Luke in his real world, who is using such a skill in addressing his Christian community and communicating to them that mission among the gentiles is replete with hurdles, and that one needs to be skillful in navigating through it. One such requirement

London: SCM, 1952), 1:77, cited in Wall, “The Acts of the Apostles,” 244.

¹⁸ Plato, *Apology* 190, cited in Johnson, “The Acts of the Apostles,” 312.

¹⁹ Johnson, “The Acts of the Apostles,” 312.

²⁰ Socrates’ defence against the charges of bringing in foreign deities was considered in the Hellenistic philosophy as model for philosophical integrity. See for instance, Lucian of Samosata, *Demonax* 11, cited in Johnson, “The Acts of the Apostles,” 313.

²¹ Wall, “The Acts of the Apostles,” 245.

²² *Ibid.*

²³ Fitzmyer, *The Acts of the Apostles*, 602.

is to begin where they are. We list below Luke's attempts (in the literary world of the text, Paul's attempts) to 'enter through their door' by referring to a few relevant aspects of both Jewish and Gentile traditions that would draw the attention of his audience. However, Luke while affirming these aspects of both the traditions, nevertheless, transcends them in his Christian interpretation.

Paul, despite being interiorly troubled by the presence of idols all over the city (Acts 17:16), nevertheless begins by appreciating their 'extreme religiosity' (v. 22). He further seeks to establish his credentials by beginning his speech with the conclusions he has drawn from what he 'carefully observed' (v. 23) at the Agora—a scholarly approach indeed. The conclusion is the affirmation that Athenians are "extremely religious in every way" (*kata panta hos deisidaimonesterous*, v. 22). Piety was considered part of being well educated in the ancient Greek world.²⁴

The unknown God of Paul's proclamation is the Creator of everything (Acts 17:24a; 4:24; 14:15; cf. Isa 42:5; Gen 1; 2:1-3; Ex 20:11); hence is the "Lord of heaven and earth" (Acts 17:24b; cf. Lk 10:21) and the source of all life (Acts 17:25), who not only creates but also sustains everything. This thought resonates with the Stoics' belief in their deity.²⁵ In Luke's community, this depiction of God has resonance both in the Greek philosophical and Jewish traditions. For instance, Pythagoras speaks of the "ordered world" as *kosmos* (Plutarch, *De placitis philosophorum* 2.1); Plato refers to 'the Maker and Father of the Universe' (Plato, *Timaeus* 28C, 76C); Epictetus depicts 'God as the maker of the cosmos' (Epictetus, Arrian's *Discourses* 4.7.6.). On the other hand, from the LXX we have Gen 1:1; 14:19, 22; Ex 20:11; Ps 145:6; Isa 42:5; Wis 9:9; 11:17; 2 Macc 7:23, 28 referring to the 'Creator God.'²⁶

²⁴ Wall, "The Acts of the Apostles," 246.

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ Fitzmyer, *The Acts of the Apostles*, 608.

Listening to Paul, on the one hand, the Epicureans would agree with him in his vehement condemnation of Athenian folk idolatry and superstition and the related beliefs in the manipulable deities (Acts 17: 25, 29), and on the other, Stoics would align with Paul in his depiction of the unity of humanity (Acts 17:26) and a kinship relationship between humans and God (Acts 17:28).²⁷ Paul thereby gains partial approval from both the parties, albeit for two different reasons.

A fundamental ‘human quest for God’ is a prevalent theme, both in the OT and some Greek philosophical traditions. For instance, Deut 4:28-29; Amos 5:6; Isa 55:6; in Seneca, *Ep.* 95.47; Cicero, *De natura deorum* 2.153 (more a philosophical quest); Philo’s *De specialibus legibus* I.7 §36 (predominantly an emotional striving) and so on.²⁸ Relatedly, the idea that God has ordained humans to seek him can be found both in the OT and in some ancient Greek literature. For instance, Wis 13:6; Isa 31:1; 55:6 and Philo’s *Special Laws* 1:32-40. Despite the opposite direction of its development, Dio Chrysostom’s *Olympic Discourse (Oration 12.60-61)* begins with the assertion that all people seek God.²⁹ A few comparable references to the human search for the divine can also be found in Philo Judaeus’ *Special Laws* 1:32-44 and Aristobulus’ *fragment 4*.³⁰ However, ‘to seek God’ in Acts 17:27 seems to refer more to the typically philosopher’s rational quest in the ancient world than to a text like Deut 4:29, where ‘seeking God’ stands primarily for a life of obedience to God.³¹

While describing the closeness of God to human beings, the Lucan Paul is generally understood to be referring to a poem that is attributed to Epimenides—one of the seven revered sages of Greece.³² The text referred to is: “In him

²⁷ Dillon, “Acts of the Apostles,” 754.

²⁸ Fitzmyer, *The Acts of the Apostles*, 609–610.

²⁹ Johnson, “The Acts of the Apostles,” 315-316.

³⁰ Ibid

³¹ Dillon, “Acts of the Apostles,” 755.

³² Cf. Diogenes Laertius, *Lives of the Philosophers* 1:109-11, cited in Johnson,

we live and move and have our being” (Acts 17:28). For Luke, it brings out a relationship more of dependence rather than any type of ontological or mystical participation in the divine.³³ That is why this relationship is further cast into a familial mould: “we are also his offsprings” (Acts 17:28, 29). Here, Luke cites the Stoic poet Aratus: *tou gar kai genos eimen* (of him we too are offspring – *Phaenomena* 5). It can also be found in *Fragment 4* of the Jewish apologist, Aristobulus. Eusebius cites it in his *Praeparatio Evangelica* 13.12.6 (GCS 8/2.194).³⁴ This type of kinship relationship for Luke moves in the direction of the Genesis depiction of the humans having been created in the ‘image and likeness’ of God (Gen 1:26).

Finally, finding no meaning in worshipping images carved by human hands is a view shared by both Jews and Greeks. The former, because of the conviction that no creature can represent the Creator and the latter because of the conviction that only a living being can stand for the Living Being.³⁵

5. BEING ‘INSIDE THE ROOM’

So far, it is about ‘entering through their door.’ We shall now witness what happens ‘inside the room,’ as it were.

The philosophers’ request, “May we know (*dynametha gnōnai*) what this new teaching is that you are presenting?” (Acts 17:19) can be taken for a polite expression. However, in the overall theological context of the text, it connotes a ‘capacity to know.’ The question is if the Greek religious-cultural and philosophical framework is *capable* (*dynametha*) of mediating to them what Paul is proclaiming. In the Lucan perspective, the answer is an emphatic ‘yes,’ as far as the starting point of such a knowing is concerned.³⁶

“The Acts of the Apostles,” 316.

³³ Johnson, “The Acts of the Apostles,” 316.

³⁴ Fitzmyer, *The Acts of the Apostles*, 611.

³⁵ H. Conzelmann, *The Theology of St. Luke* (London: Faber and Faber, 1960), 224, cited in Dillon, “Acts of the Apostles,” 755.

³⁶ Johnson, “The Acts of the Apostles,” 320.

However, at some point they need to transcend their current epistemic categories if they have to embrace faith in Christ Jesus. However, despite his borrowing certain items from Greek socio-cultural world, the real Paul in 1 Cor 1:18-25 has a rather negative valuation of their wisdom systems. Obviously, Luke in Acts is not facing Paul's Corinthian audience. Be that as it may, for our purpose, it is important to know how Lucan Paul at Athens or Luke himself in his real world would proceed with this audience.

The Lucan Paul now switches over to pointing at the 'ignorance' of the Athenians in their worship of the 'unknown god' (*Agnostos Theos* – Acts 17:23) and thereby at their 'worship done unknowingly.' The verb *katangellō* (proclaim) (Acts 17:3) is used to signify Church's mission of proclaiming the Gospel (see Acts 3:24; 4:2; 13:5, 38; 15:36; 16:17; 17:3). It is clear that Paul is on such a mission at Athens. However, accusing Paul of trying to introduce 'strange deities' (Acts 17:18) does not hold, since he is only unveiling the God who is already worshipped there, albeit unknowingly.³⁷ Indeed they belong to the 'time of ignorance' (Acts 17:30) despite being in the city of scholars! Pauline irony prepares the grounds for laying bare the purpose of his coming to Athens: he has come to proclaim that very God whom the Athenians unknowingly worship (Acts 17:23). Is he not then bringing an end to their time of ignorance rather than introducing strange deities, as he is accused of?

Further, because "we are God's offspring, we ought not to think that the deity is like gold, or silver, or stone, an image formed by the art and imagination of mortals" (Acts 17:29). What is suggested is not to consider "the divine" (*to theion*—a term used only here in the New Testament) in images that are non-rational in nature.³⁸

³⁷ E. Haenchen, *The Acts of the Apostles* (Philadelphia: Westminster, 1971), 521, cited in Wall, "The Acts of the Apostles," 246.

³⁸ Johnson, "The Acts of the Apostles," 316-317

Paul views the insights of the Greek poet through the Genesis lens to critique the Athenian idolatry. Indeed we find a similar critique in Deut 4:28; Ps 135:15; Isa 40:18-19; 44:9-20; Wis 13:4, 10; 15:3-17; Rom 1:23. Such a critique is also found in a Hellenistic philosopher like Dio Chrysostom in his *Oration* 12.80-83.

The Lucan Paul's idea of 'God does not live in temples made by human hands' (Acts 17:24) has a dual resonance: one in the OT (cf. 1 Kings 8:27; Isa 57:15) and the other in the Stoic philosopher Zeno: "It is Zeno's teaching that one should not build temples of the gods" (Plutarch, *Moralia* 1034B). A similar text is found also in a *fragment* of Euripides (968): "What house fashioned by builders can contain the divine form within enclosing walls?"³⁹ Indeed Isa 66:1-2 supports this thought. Lucan critique of the feeding of the gods at the Athenian worship practices (Acts 17:25) has resonance both in the OT and Greek philosophical traditions: Ps 50:9-12; Amos 5:21-22; 2 Macc 14:35; Aristobulus, *fragment* 4; cf. Eusebius, *Praeparatio Evangelica* 13.12.3. Indeed Euripides said, "For God, if indeed God he be, is in need of nothing" (*Hercules Furens* 1345-46).⁴⁰ Paul also implicitly appeals to the common sense; namely, the Athenian practices of building shrines and offering food to deities (Acts 17:25) contradict the belief in God's own transcendent and living nature. The type of worship needs to suit the nature of the Deity. The Athenian worship fails to measure up to this maxim.⁴¹ Indeed such illogical practices prove that idolatry belongs to the time of ignorance (*chronos agnoias*).⁴² In keeping with the composition of his audience, Luke draws from both Jewish and Greek traditions to make his point.

Although Paul, in Rom 1:20, attributes culpability for the

³⁹ Lactantius, *Divinae Institutiones* 6.25J, cited in Fitzmyer, *The Acts of the Apostles*, 608.

⁴⁰ Fitzmyer, *The Acts of the Apostles*, 608.

⁴¹ Wall, "The Acts of the Apostles," 248.

⁴² Ibid.

failure to recognize God to humans, nevertheless the Lucan Paul's depiction of God's mercy regarding this failure (Acts 17:30) is in tandem with Paul's own thought in Rom 3:25; 11:32; and 1 Cor 1:21. Hence in Paul's reckoning, God in his merciful benevolence "overlooks" the human ignorance and invites them to repent (Acts 17:30). In this way, the 'God of mercy' of Luke's Gospel does find a continuity in Paul's own preaching. Since this mercy of God is universal in reach, Athenians too can benefit from it, if only they can turn away from the idols.⁴³ Indeed, God's redeeming judgment overshadows any trace of condemnation in the Lucan Paul's deliberation.

With these considerations, the Lucan Paul prepares for his central appeal by saying that God the Creator has a definite plan for his creation (Acts 17: 26-28a). According to this plan, God has created the humans in such a way that "humans would search for God and perhaps grope for him and find him" (Acts 17:27a). As mentioned above, such a seeking for God is found in both Jewish and Greek traditions. These considerations make a launching pad now to proclaim "the Creator God [who] makes just such a world to deliver them all from divine judgment."⁴⁴

In this context, the core of Paul's message is that, the Risen Jesus is the God-appointed redeeming judge over the world and his resurrection is the offer of assurance of this appointment (Acts 17:31) — "the point where propaedeutic theodicy reaches out to Christian *kerygma*, and likewise the point where the *kerygma* predictably repels many of its educated prospects."⁴⁵ The concepts such as 'offer of assurance' (*parechō pistin*) (Acts 17:31), if understood as giving a pledge, is found in Herodotus' *Persian Wars* 3.74. If it is taken as a demonstration, it is reflected in Aristotle's

⁴³ Ibid.

⁴⁴ Ibid., 247.

⁴⁵ G. Schneider, "Apg 17, 22-31," in *Kontextualität und Einheit: Festschrift für Franz Mussner*, ed. P.-G. Müller (Freiburg, 1981), 233, cited in Dillon, "Acts of the Apostles," 754.

Nicomachean Ethics 1173A and Josephus' *Antiquities of the Jews* 15.69.⁴⁶ In the second case, the Lucan Gentile- and Jewish Christian audience clearly understand the significance of this 'assurance'; for, it solves their theodicean query in the context of the fall of the Jerusalem temple: if God is still faithful to his promises. Indeed God is!

Lucan Paul, in his proclamation, neither demonizes nor rejects "some of your own poets" (Acts 17:28). In fact, a few other items of Greek socio-cultural world are referred to in the Pauline corpus itself.⁴⁷ In fact, they serve as starting points for him to dialogue with the gentile cultures. Here Luke is faithful to what the real Paul did in his mission among the gentiles. The shrines to gods, religious poetry, philosophy, and so on are expressions of the insatiable human longing for the Ultimate. Paul, Lucan or otherwise, only points at the way for the real fulfilment of such a longing for God: the risen Lord, Jesus Christ. Would the Athenian addressees of Lucan Paul or those of Luke himself in his real world repent and follow the way shown by him?

6. COMING OUT THROUGH HIS DOOR

Would the Athenians accept Paul's invitation? Perhaps the *hoi poloi* at the Agora may have had difficulties in giving up the idols, while the intellectuals (Stoics and Epicureans) would have found it relatively easier. But the Athenian intellectuals are not at ease with Paul's proclamation about the Resurrection of Jesus. It sounds strange to them (Acts 17:32a).

⁴⁶ Johnson, "The Acts of the Apostles," 316.

⁴⁷ For instance in the proto and deutro Pauline letters we find these images: citizenship Language (Phil 3:20); ambassador (*presbeuō*) (2 Cor 5:20); Rom 1:20 reflects the Stoic or Platonic ideas of perceiving divine truth through nature and reason; household codes (*oikonomia*) in Eph 5–6; Col 3–4; from the world of Greek sports: Running a Race (1 Cor 9:24-27), Boxing (1 Cor 9:26), Wrestling/Fighting (Eph 6:12), the victor's crown (*stephanos*) (2 Tim 4:8), striving/competing (*athleō*) (2 Tim 2:5), the prize (*brabeion*) (Phil 3:14), athlete's self-control (*enkrateia*) (1 Cor 9:25), the stadium/arena imagery (*stadion*) (1 Cor 9:24), perishable vs imperishable wreath (*stephanos aphthartos*) (1 Cor 9:25).

At this the Lucan Paul exits; but how? What are the results? Paul leaves the place (Acts 17:33); however not without some fruits of his labour: Dionysius and Damaris and a few others become believers (Acts 17:34). Dionysius, being an Areopagite, a member of the Athenian council belongs to the higher echelons of the Athenian society.⁴⁸ In fact, Eusebius identifies this Dionysius as the first “shepherd of the diocese of the Corinthians.”⁴⁹ Indeed Acts 17:12 qualifies some of the converts as “men of high standing.” The inclusion of women in the Christian fold—in this case Damaris, is also found in Acts 16:14; 17:4, 12. The *Codex Bezae* qualifies Damaris as *euschemon* (respectable) and the *Codex Basilensis* as *timia* (honourable).⁵⁰ With such description of the converts, Luke seem to be affirming that the foundations for a later Church of Christ is laid at the end of Paul’s speech.⁵¹

The Areopagus episode marks one of the many historic encounters between ‘Jerusalem’ and ‘Athens,’ though its actual historicity during Paul’s visit to Athens would have been less dramatic than what Luke has depicted. However, it foreshadows the whole course of later history of the Christianized Hellenistic culture with all its lights and shadows.⁵² In this sense, it is symbolic of several encounters between the Christian gospel and the ‘nations.’⁵³ Given the fact that the central motif of the Acts is to show the continuity between God’s salvific plan in the OT and that in Jesus Christ, which includes all those who repent—Jews

⁴⁸ Aristotle, *Politics* 1273B – 1274A, cited in Johnson, “The Acts of the Apostles,” 318.

⁴⁹ Eusebius of Caesarea, *Ecclesiastical History*, 3.4.10, trans. Kirsopp Lake, in *The Loeb Classical Library*, vol. 1 (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1926). Cited in Fitzmyer, *The Acts of the Apostles*, 613.

⁵⁰ Fitzmyer, *The Acts of the Apostles*, 613.

⁵¹ Wall, “The Acts of the Apostles,” 248.

⁵² In the context of Gnostic and philosophical distortions of Christian doctrine, Tertullian in the second century inquired with a tone of lamentation: “What has Athens to do with Jerusalem?” – *De Praescriptione Haereticorum (On the Prescription of Heretics)*, chapter 7.

⁵³ Johnson, “The Acts of the Apostles,” 318.

and gentiles alike, the Areopagus episode forms a concrete expression of it.

The Lucan Paul used the insights of Greek poets to make his point intelligible and acceptable to the philosophers at the Areopagus. We can see here three types of responses: some sneered at him when he spoke of the resurrection of the dead.⁵⁴ In some, Paul's speech created mild ripples⁵⁵ and they said, "We will hear you again about this" (Acts 17:32); and a few along with Dionysius and Damaris accepted Paul's message (Acts 17:34).

The important thing to note is this: Paul did not get stuck in 'their space' by compromising the foundation of his faith – Jesus and his resurrection – for the sake of greater acceptability. Nor did he come through 'his own door,' as much as he might have desired to, by having all of them converted to the Gospel. Acts 17:32-34 shows that their initial curiosity for the 'new' did not make many of them accept Paul's message. Paul could have been tempted to keep their curiosity boiling by saying something not really in tandem with the Gospel. But he did not do so. Instead, he exited from the scene with a limited success.

7. IMPLICATIONS FOR OUR LIFE-MISSION

Have we experienced embarrassment due to our faithfulness to the Lord, or only praise, honour, and exaltation in our life-mission? We see a mixture of these in the mission of Jesus of Nazareth. At times he was highly exalted, people even wanted to make him their king by force (Jn 6:15) and yet at times they rejected him (Mt 13:57). We see many an embarrassing situation in his life: when he spoke the truth, many of his

⁵⁴ The idea of resurrection is mocked at on the basis of Apollos' affirmation, "[W]hen the dust has soaked up the blood of a man, once he has died, there is no resurrection" (*outis est anastasis*) - Aeschylus, *Eumenides* 647-48). Cited in Fitzmyer, *The Acts of the Apostles*, 612.

⁵⁵ This type of interpretation as against a polite (cynical?) but firm rejection is given by C. K. Barrett, "Paul's Speech on the Areopagus," in *New Testament Christianity for Africa and the World: Essays in Honour of Harry Sawyerr*, ed. M. E. Glasswell and E. W. Fasholé-Luke (London: SPCK, 1974), 71 and others. Referred to in Fitzmyer, *The Acts of the Apostles*, 612.

disciples stopped following him (Jn 6:66); to his own possible embarrassment, his own family came to take him away by force because people were saying, he had gone out of his mind (Mk 3:21); his disciples were puzzled and may have even been embarrassed seeing him speaking to a Samaritan woman (Jn 4:27); Peter was embarrassed when he began to wash his feet (Jn 13:6) —a strange gesture on the part of a teacher and master; at the trial scene all deserted him; and all this peaked on the cross—the greatest of all embarrassments, feeling abandoned by God his Father despite his staunch faith in him (Mt 27:46; Mk 15:34).

Being called “babblers” (*spermologoi*) due to our faithfulness to the Lord becomes a strong proof of our fidelity. Do we have the wisdom and courage to accept this fact? Today we speak of the ‘need for changing with times and moving ahead with the contemporary currents.’ One can affirm the validity and the necessity of such a stance. However, doesn’t this at times risk ending up in being *in* the world and also being *of* the world? We speak of ‘entering through their door and coming out through ours.’ Doesn’t the type of diplomacy and public relations we exercise, at times make us enter through ‘their door’ and comfortably settle down there? Jesus went for a dinner to Simon the Pharisee’s house (Lk 7:36f). But the dinner that he enjoyed did not stop him from saying what he wanted to say to Simon, his host. Haven’t we at times allowed ourselves to be chained and gagged by the favours we receive from the powers that be? Doesn’t our loud silence in the face of blatant injustice meted out to people of other faiths and other denominations stem from our fear of losing our privileges and preferential treatment?

The episode of cleansing of the Temple (Jn 2:13-25) makes it amply clear that worship and unjust commerce cannot go together, just as one cannot serve both, God and Mammon. The unjust trade relations of our times have enabled a few to amass unimaginable amounts of wealth and power at the cost of depriving millions of even the basic facilities of life.

Active promotion of consumerism has become absolutely essential to keep up today's globalized economy. Can the Christian educational institutions in general and the business schools run by the Christian entities in particular afford to deviate from this norm? What alternative visions are we living by and instilling in others today? Are we really forming 'men and women for and with others' or men and women for keeping up the exploitative political-economies? It would be inconvenient, nay naive and embarrassing even to raise such questions as these, in a world where the atrocious principles of global economy and foreign policy are considered as 'common sense.' However the Lucan Paul did not hesitate to speak about 'Jesus and his Resurrection' even when it escaped the 'common sense' of the Athenian intellectuals. Playing to the gallery was not his practice. Should it be of a disciple of Jesus today?

CONCLUSION

The Athenian worship of an unknown God, done unknowingly, resembles the situation of responding to the genuine, deep-seated human longing for the true God by bowing down in worship to the idols of our own making—power, pleasure, success, and control. Indeed, the oft-quoted line from St. Augustine, "You have made us for yourself, O Lord, and our heart is restless until it rests in you," implies that even in sin, the human heart seeks God, albeit in vain. This is what Paul saw in Athens: a city drowning in idols yet gasping for transcendence. However, Paul's mission was not to shame the city but to unveil the truth—to awaken its people to the God they unknowingly craved.

The mission of a disciple of Jesus consists precisely in bringing to the awareness of individuals and groups their deep-seated longing for God, as Paul did with his audience. To be sure, it won't be a mission of comfort, nor a stage for applause. It will not succeed if the disciple were to merely play to the gallery, echoing the crowd's desires.